

The proof of Euclid's fifth postulate

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Abstract. In this paper a study has been carried out in the field of foundations of geometry. The way of comprehension of man, the initial concepts in geometry like point, straight line, plane, infinity and space has been studied. Their importance in the structure of axiomatics of geometry and the whole science is determined. The geometrical model of space is constructed and the mystery of the theory of parallel lines is revealed. In this article completely new decisions and approaches to understanding space are adopted whereupon mathematics obtains previously lost certainty and rigor in building the foundations of geometry and the whole science of mathematics. The model of geometric space presented in the article is the beginning of all mathematics, including Euclidean axiomatics, and is confirmed by the observation of flat astronomical space.

1 INTRODUCTION

The history of the raised in the article issue covers time over two thousand years of mathematics development. Nowadays mathematical science has acquired tranquility and versatility of the issues to be solved in physics, astronomy and other sciences. It would seem that there are no unsolvable questions for mathematics, since any complex questions of many sciences are solved by mathematicians, and to what extent this corresponds to the rigor and deductive logic of the structure of mathematics itself, for more than a hundred years, is no longer important. Unfortunately, the history of science knows much longer time periods of tranquility and narcissism. Let me remind you about the existence of the geocentric planetary system of Ptolemy 1500 years ago and how hard it was for N. Copernicus, J. Kepler and Galileo Galilei to break the centuries-old world view. Now the situation in science isn't better than in the previous period of tranquility and in order to move away from this narcissism we need to provide scientific society with facts about the existence of new theories and new views on mathematics, physics, astronomy, philosophy and other sciences. It's the only way humanity can understand that it stays in the abyss of illusion and self-deception in understanding the secrets of the world creation.

Let's ask ourselves a philosophical question that everyone will understand. Say you are a fisherman and you are going to fish in the field or on the pavement instead of going to the pond. Can you catch fish there? Maybe yes, if you can call empty cans of canned fish as fish. It is easy to imagine what kind of discovery a scientist can make if he has a geocentric understanding of the world. He will accept a new fantastic hypothesis, a mathematician will describe it in formulas, in the end humanity will be even farther in a web of lies, lagging behind the process of science and technology.

Mathematics is one of the fundamental sciences of space, but only by putting in order mathematical thought and parallel sciences, we can talk about comprehending the truth of the whole universe. After I have read the works of the American mathematician Morris Kline and the Soviet mathematician A. Aleksandrov, I was very glad that I am not alone in such thoughts, their works are full of deep perception of problems in science. Therefore for a better understanding of parallel line studies the part of the text is devoted to the historical overview, in which you can gradually trace the path of the opinion-forming on the geometric point, a straight line, space and

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other initial designations, needed later for the construction of the geometry axiomatics. This approach to presenting information allows you to reveal the historical theme about parallel lines theory. It will be available not only to narrow specialists as mathematicians but also understandable to a wide range of readers.

2 THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNDERSTANDING SPACE.

BRIEF HISTORY

From the handwritten works of the ancient Greek culture, it is known that the first germs of mathematics, astronomy and other sciences appeared in Egypt more than 2000 years BC. In ancient Egypt one of the most educated people were priests, who were engaged in spiritual life, architecture, astronomy, healing and other sciences, which were in demand in the society of that time. Watching the stars and other celestial bodies, they most likely could predict the flood of the Nile, different periods of solstice and many other natural phenomena. It is known that the word geometry comes from the Ancient Greek words *Earth* and *measurement*, from which we can conclude that mathematics was born due to the demand of people to solve their everyday problems. When the Nile spilled, all boundaries of land plots blurred and it was necessary to re-establish various geometric plots of fertile land. For this purpose, the Egyptians used thin ropes, stretched between two pegs. This is how the first understanding of dots (pegs) was formed and a rope is a segment of a straight line, which length is not specified, but can grow limitlessly. Some people think that if people in the early days of mathematics knew that the Earth was round, they would initially take a straight line curved. But from the works of Aristotle it is known that the scientists of that time knew that the Earth had a spherical shape. Nevertheless, at that time there was a mandatory requirement for a straight line as the shortest distance from one place to another. If we measure land on a spherical surface using ropes and pegs, at a great distance these pegs should be of sufficient height, while pulling the thread it should not touch the sphere. After all the Ancient Egyptians, the Babylonians, the Greeks understood that going straight is always shorter than going on a curve. A great leap forward the development of all sciences occurred in Ancient Greece between the 6th and the 2nd centuries BC. The Greeks picked up the initial knowledge of science from the Egyptians and raised many sciences to the level of initially built, consistently constructed and logically grounded sciences. Philosophy, astronomy and mathematics have raised special development. Therefore, at that time not only geometry was born, but also arithmetic, algebra, trigonometry and mathematical analysis. Despite the fact that the society of that time worshiped a galaxy of gods, many scientists were critical of their contemporaries' beliefs. They expressed thoughts in relation to gods and freely presented various ideas and hypothesis of the beginning of the world creation. Aristotle believed that the Earth was round and was located in the center of the universe and the starry sky and objects on it were moving along the surfaces of individual spheres. Aristarch of Samos, who lived in 340–230 BC, suggested that the Sun did not move, the Earth was rotating around the Sun and simultaneously around its axis. In addition, he was the first who suggested the mathematical possibility of measuring the distance to the Moon and the Sun. Unfortunately, his thoughts were not shared by the scientific community of that time. Probably humanity has no short ways to learn the truth, we necessarily must go through various false paths in order to find a simple short path eventually. After a change in the political situation, Rome conquered the territory adjacent to the Mediterranean at the end of the 1st century BC, the Ancient Greek culture got damaged. Thousands of Greek books were burnt, the famous library of Alexandria died in a fire, where the most valuable collections of ancient manuscripts were kept. Later Rome took an irreconcilable position in relation to the Greek pagan culture, they even ridiculed mathematics, astronomy and

other natural sciences.

Instead of forbidden gods, the belief in one God and his envoy Jesus Christ was gaining strength. The Roman emperor Constantine the Great proclaimed Christianity the official religion of the Roman Empire in 313 AD. All pagan temples were destroyed on the basis of the decree of 392 AD. The Ideology of that time glorified a man as specially sent by one God to the Earth and it meant that the Earth was the center of the universe. That's why the church clergy accepted the theory of the motion of celestial bodies, proposed by Aristotle and further scientifically developed by Ptolemy. It has survived to this day in the essay of Arab scholars called "Almagest". The, because of impermissible rule of the church and permanent wars for redistribution of Euro-Asia and North Africa, the whole science developed very slowly. The accepted religious dogmas about the creation of the world only hindered its development. In the 16th century Nicolaus Copernicus, while studying the miraculously survived works of Greek scientists, came across Aristarch of Samoa's hypothesis about the heliocentric planetary model of the world. Accepting this assumption, he noticed that Ptolemy's existing theory of planetary motion greatly simplified by placing the Sun at a resting center. Then Johannes Kepler (1571–1630) finalized his work. J. Kepler had studied the nature of five planets in the solar system motion, known at that time, and through mathematical formulas emphasized three laws of celestial bodies motion.

Italian scientist Galileo Galilei has made a great contribution to the understanding of space. The telescope was invented at the beginning of the 17th century, and after Galileo heard about it he made a telescope. Watching the night sky, he noticed that Jupiter is like the Earth, it has moons. This discovery meant Jupiter could have natural satellites, and this invention destroyed the ideology of the church that God created the Earth and a man on it. A man like all sky bodies became ordinary wanderers in cold heavenly vastness of the universe. The church inquisition forced Galileo to renounce his beliefs publicly, but his thoughts had been already published and it was impossible to stop them. In addition to discoveries in astronomy, Galileo developed mathematical formulas for the motion of bodies, he laid the foundations for understanding inertia and the theory of relativity of motion. Later X. Wren, J. Wallis, C. Huygens, R. Hooke and R. Descartes supplemented his works on mechanics but all their workings were uncoordinated and had no general justification for physical space.

Later, Isaac Newton relied on J. Kepler's pattern of solar system planets motion and derived a mathematical formula for the law of gravitation, thereby he united the movement on the Earth and in space. Newton's theory of bodies motion at that time explained the movement of bodies on the Earth and in the universe. At the end of the 18th century, all sciences of space, including mathematics, took a well deserved leading place after more than four thousand years of science development.

3 REVOLUTION OF IDEAS IN UNDERSTANDING SPACE. NON-EUCLIDEAN GEOMETRY

The content of definitions, postulates and axioms, published in "The Elements" by Euclid, is attached below for the best understanding (before statements [1, b.1, pp.11... 15]):

Definitions

- 1. Point is something, which has no parts.*
- 2. Line is length without width.*
- 3. The ends of the lines are dots.*
- 4. A straight line is one that is equally located in relation to the points on it.*
- 5. The surface is something that has only length and width.*

6. *The ends of the surface are lines.*
7. *A flat surface is one that is equally located in relation to the straight lines on it.*
8. *A flat angle is the inclination of two lines to each other, meeting each other in the plane, but not in a straight line.*
9. *When the lines containing the angle are straight, the angle is called rectilinear.*
10. *When a straight line, restored on another straight line, forms equal among themselves angles then each of equal angles is straight and the restored straight line is called the perpendicular to the one on which it is restored.*
11. *Obtuse angle is bigger than the right one.*
12. *Acute angle is less than the right one.*
13. *Border is the finish of something.*
14. *Figure is something that is contained within a border.*
15. *Circle is a flat figure, contained within one line called circumference, on which all lines are from one point within the shape, falling on a circumference, are equal to each other.*
16. *This point is called the center of the circle.*
17. *The diameter of the circle is any straight line, drawn through the center and limited on both sides of the circumference of the circle and it also cuts the circle in half.*
18. *Semicircle is a figure contained between the diameter and the part of the circle it cuts off. The center of the semicircle is the same as that of the circle.*
19. *Rectilinear figures are those that are contained between the straight lines, three-sided figures are figures contained between three straight lines, four-sided figures are figures contained between four straight lines, multi-sided figures are figures contained between more than four straight lines.*
20. *Among three-sided figures, an equilateral triangle is a figure, which has three equal sides, an isosceles triangle has only two equal sides and a versatile triangle has three unequal sides.*
21. *A right-angled triangle is triangle with a right angle, an obtuse triangle has an obtuse angle, an acute-angled triangle has three acute angles.*
22. *Among four-sided figures, a square is both equal-sided and rectangular figure, versatile is a rectangular but not equilateral figure, rhombus is an equilateral but not rectangular figure, parallelogram is neither equilateral nor rectangular figure, which has opposite sides and angles equal to each other. Other four-sided figures will be called trapezes.*
23. *Parallel straight lines are lines, being in the same plane and being extended in both directions, without limit, do not meet with each other.*

Postulates

Let's say:

1. *You can draw a straight line from every point to any point.*
2. *A limited straight line can be continued permanently in a straight line.*
3. *A circle can be described from any center and any solution.*
4. *All right angles are equal to each other.*
5. *If a straight line, falling on other two straight lines, forms internal angles on one side, which are less than two straight lines, then these continued two straight lines will meet unlimited times on the side, where the angles are less than two straight lines.*

Axioms

1. *Equal to the same are equal to each other.*
2. *If equals are added to equals, then the integers will be equal.*
3. *If equal is subtracted from equals, the remainders will be equal.*
4. *If equal are added to not equal, then the integers will be not equal.*
5. *Doubles of the same are equal to each other.*
6. *Halves of the same are equal to each other.*
7. *Combined with each other are equal to each other.*
8. *The whole is more than a part.*
9. *Two straight lines do not contain space.*

Then Euclid, relying on definitions previously adopted without proof, solves problems and proves theorems. To make sure of the correctness of scientific thought in the construction of axioms and all mathematics, a mandatory rule must be followed — a logical sequence of accepted statements. Therefore, Euclid, when constructing mathematics, fulfills a necessary condition: all floors of the science building are built on the basis of the previously laid foundation (axioms) and theorems, that are located on the lower floors of the building. Moreover, the arguments of theorems and axiomatic of the upper sections of mathematics are not used.

As we can see from the initial text of the book “The elements”, Euclid all initial geometric concepts accepts without proof and divides them into three categories. In order to understand why he is doing this we need to be imbued with that time in which the great mathematician lived and worked. Many works of the ancient philosopher Aristotle have remained until now (384–322 BC). Euclid lived and worked later (325–265 BC) and of course he possessed knowledge of the beginning of everything, which are set out in the work of Aristotle “The metaphysics”. So Aristotle says [2, b.3, ch.2, p.51]: “...*If there is a science which gives proof, there must be some common genus at the heart of this science. And some of these beginnings will be known properties of this genus, and others will be axioms (because there can be no proof for everything without exception): the point is that any proof must be given on the basis of something in relation to something and to justify something. It turns out the whole set of what is being proved belongs to one general genus, as all proving sciences apply axioms*”. In light of the foregoing, Aristotle sets the rules for building a logically grounded provable science. Further in the text, he states [2, b.3, ch.2, p.52]: “...*axioms have the highest degree of generality and represent the beginning of everything*”. Reasoning of the truth about the beginnings, he says [2, b.3, ch.3, p.56]: “...*Based on these considerations, we can say that genus is not the beginning of things. As we learn everything through definitions, and genus is their beginning, genus should also be the beginning for those things, which are indicated through the definitions. If you achieve the knowledge of things, you achieve the knowledge of genus, according to which things are named. Genus is the beginning of species*”. In his work “Metaphysics” Aristotle expresses many necessary requirements for building the beginnings of any science. But he can’t gain an understanding of the initial foundational definitions in mathematics. Aristotle understands the abstraction of geometric figures, plane, lines and points but he can not separate them from sensation and material things. He writes [2, b.3, ch.5, p.67]: “...*Points, lines and plane can’t arise and can’t be destroyed, sometimes they exist and sometimes they stop existing. When objects come into contact, one value is formed immediately from their boundary points, lines and surfaces. When the objects are separate, two values are formed. Thus, by joining objects, the former boundary no longer exists. When separating objects, boundaries, which did not exist before,*

appear (an indivisible point could not split in two). If boundaries arise and disappear, where do they come from?''. Thus, we can see that during Euclid's time points and lines a priori couldn't exist, they must have been associated with sensation or matter. This why Euclid follows the rules adopted by Aristotle, through the definitions he introduces the concept of a point, a straight line, geometric figures and postulates (axioms), intended for the provable science of geometry. Next com general concepts (axioms according to Aristotle), they have the greatest degree of generality and can be applied to other sciences.

Analyzing Euclid's work, you understand what a correct and verified decision he made in his time. Despite the prevailing uncertainty in understanding a line, a point and plane, he rejected the ambiguity of geometric concepts. For Euclid, in the foundations of science all definitions and general concepts, regardless of their name, bear the status of self-evident axioms. From the historical past, we see how difficult it was for Euclid to give the correct definition of a point and a straight line, how important and significant is the presence of these definitions in the axiomatics of geometry foundations. Any geometric concept, accepted without proof, in the future will have a force comparable to a seed from which a large tree of science will gradually grow.

Many centuries "The elements" by Euclid was appropriate for humanity, but the fifth postulate was questionable. Some mathematicians believed that the formulation of the parallel lines axiom was too complicated and it lacked the simplicity of other axioms. They attempted to change the formulation of the fifth postulate and prove it as a theorem based on the rest of the axioms. These attempts were unsuccessful and did not lead to anything. Russian mathematician Nikolai Lobachevsky (1792–1856) had been dealing with the problem of parallel lines for a long time. The attempts to prove the fifth postulate did not lead Lobachevsky to the desired results. Then he made the decision to abandon the search of a proof and create a geometry different from Euclid. For this he had changed the axiom of parallel lines to its opposite, assuming that through a point outside a given straight line on the same plane passed at least two lines parallel to a given. Building the axiomatics of his theory, N. Lobachevsky tried to build a logical system of axioms, equal to Euclid's geometry. At the same time, he didn't notice that he initially violated the principle of logical consistency and rigor of constructing the foundations of geometry, laid down by Euclid. In his geometry, Lobachevsky did not introduce the definition of a point and a straight line, but they are not less significant in the construction of axiomatics than the fifth postulate. This seemingly insignificant deviation in the presentation of the principles is not permissible, since each definition in the axiomatics of geometry is equivalent in significance to the postulate of parallel lines. Euclid simply gave the axioms different names based on the works of the wise thinker Aristotle. Later, this error of Lobachevsky leads to the formation of a false worldview in science, which does not allow many researchers to discover the truth of nature to this day. He gave a public lecture about this geometry in 1826 and his extensive work was published in 1830. The meaning of this geometry remained unclear because there was no model where the interpretation of the developed geometry was performed. The Hungarian mathematician Janos Boyai, without knowing about Lobachevsky's work, published a scientific work with the presentation of the same results of the new theory of space. The German scientist Carl Friedrich Gauss conducted his research in this direction, he didn't publish his work during his lifetime, but left in it in a manuscript. His contemporaries did not accept Lobachevsky's scientific work, after its publication. Carl Gauss also remained silent, apparently he had doubts about the structure of non-Euclidean geometries. For many years after the publication of Lobachevsky and Boyai, mathematicians ignored a new geometry. Almost all of them believed that the only true geometry of space should be Euclidean geometry. However, after Gauss's death in 1855, by the way, his reputation as an astronomer was unusually high, his correspondence became

known and the materials of his manuscripts were discovered. After their publication, the public learnt that he himself was working on the opportunity to construct and develop other geometry. It should be mentioned, that Gauss had a very responsible approach toward the publication of his works. When he saw there was a contradiction in some theory, he did not step over his doubts and did not do hasty acts only for the sake of his primacy in science and gaining suspicious fame. Unfortunately, as we see from the further development of all science, after the Gauss's death, the time of scientists responsible for science and society has gone forever. Therefore, after the publication of Gauss's thoughts, for a period of about 40 years, many mathematicians were offered a variety of new models of geometry. Non-Euclidean geometry differs from Euclidean geometry only in the shape of a straight line. Euclid's straight line is determined by the axiomatics from the book "The elements", set out at the beginning of the article. Initially, introducing the concept of a point, a straight line and plane, building the foundations of the geometry, Euclid gets a triangle with the sum of its interior angles 180° (fig. 1, left). Non-Euclidean geometries, while constructing, also rely on a straight line. However, a straight line is assumed to be curved and the geometry model determines the shape of curvature. It is assumed that the bend of a straight line is very slight and visible only on astronomical scales. For better understanding of non-Euclidean geometry, let us construct a triangle on Euclidean plane, using curved straight lines. Then we will

Figure 1. Triangles in geometry. From left to right: Euclidean, on the sphere, Lobachevsky's.

have two versions of non-Euclidean geometry, when the sum of the interior angles of the triangle is less than 180° (fig. 1, on right), the geometry of Lobachevsky is implemented. In the second variant, the sum of the inner angles of the triangle is greater than 180° , geometry on a sphere is performed (fig. 1, in the center). Because of the original concept of a straight line, various models of new non-Euclidean geometries were built, different from Euclidean space. In the model of Italian mathematician Eugenio Beltrami (1835–1900) Lobachevsky's geometry is carried out on the surface of the pseudosphere (fig. 2, left). Straight lines are considered as the shortest distance between the points located on the pseudosphere, where lines B and C intersect at point A and are parallel to line D . The pseudosphere is called the surface of constant negative curvature, where the sum of the interior angles of a triangle is always less than 180° . Figure 2 (in the center) shows the model on the surface of the ball: it is believed that a straight line on a sphere is any circumference of a great circle, obtained when a plane intersects with the sphere, passing through the center of the ball. In this model, on a surface with positive curvature, the sum of the interior angles of a triangle always greater than 180° , all straight lines intersect each other, so it does not implement neither Euclidean nor Lobachevsky's geometries. As we have shown that there are geometric models with positive and negative curvature, it is easy to understand that there is zero curvature on the ordinary Euclidean plane. The German mathematician Felix Klein pointed out a simpler geometry model of Lobachevsky's which was also implicitly contained in the work of the English mathematician Arthur Cayley. In this model (fig. 2, on right) the role of the plane is played by the interior of the unit circle on the ordinary Euclidean plane. Points in the model are

points inside the circle; chords with excluded ends serve as straight lines; parts of chords are line segments. The illustration shows that all axioms of Euclidean geometry are fulfilled inside the circle, except for the fifth postulate. As we can see, there are limited geometry models, in which all the axioms of planimetry are realized, except for the axiom of parallel lines. This indicates the independence of the parallelism axiom from other axioms. At the same time it is the proof of the consistency of Lobachevsky's geometry, this opinion still exists in science. More detail, Cayley-Klein the model described in § 39 and § 40 of A. Aleksandrov's book [5].

Many mathematicians saw that, while constructing non-Euclidean models of geometry, the requirements for a straight line, laid down by Euclid's axioms, were not followed. The mathematics of that time acted very simply in response to these objections, thus in 1882 Moritz Pasch published a study on the foundations of geometry. In this study, he states that the basic position of geometry should be borrowed from experience, but further development must follow a purely logical path. He tried to adjust his axiomatics to the already known models of non-Euclidean geometry. In his axioms he talks about segments and pieces of a plane, which are taken as some sets of points, but what should be understood as a point and a straight line is not defined. All you need to know about them is formulated in axioms, however, Pasch's axioms were too cumbersome, and he could not achieve compactness and brevity. In 1899 D. Gilbert's (1862–1943) work "Foundations of geometry" appeared, which was then repeatedly supplemented and edited.

Figure 2. Non-Euclidean geometries. From left to right: Beltrami's model, geometry model on a sphere, Cayley-Klein model.

It is believed that the main merit of Gilbert lies in the fact that he was able to construct the axiomatics of geometry, as the result of its partitioning into separate groups of axioms, which made it possible to formulate the axioms in the simplest way. When constructing axiomatics, Gilbert refuses to define geometric concepts — for him they are just thinkable things that satisfy the axioms. In his book "Foundations of geometry" (1899) [3, p.221], he stated: "... *that although we use such words as a point, a straight line and so on, it is quite possible to talk about beer mugs, chairs and any other objects as long as they satisfy the axioms*". Analyzing the accepted now axiomatics (non-Euclidean geometries), one wonders how this could happen, as there is no logic of reasoning in non-Euclidean geometries. In addition to the above about beer mugs, the models themselves are presented in the form of bodies and figures that is in the form of separate parts of an integral space or planes and from these separate fragments, we can't imagine an infinite geometric space without voids. The Ancient Greeks taught us that a part of the whole couldn't be the whole of something. Besides, all the presented models of space and the elements of geometry included in them are described by complex mathematical functions. These formulas of surfaces and lines are not the elements of the beginning of geometry, they are in the spheres of knowledge of algebra and mathematical analysis. Thereby, the rules of logical sequence and construction of the principles of science, laid down by Euclid, are violated. If we ask ourselves why this happened, we will find no answer. The creator of quantum mechanics Max Planck [3, p.105] said: "*New scientific truth wins not because its opponents are convinced*

of its correctness, but only for the reason that opponents are gradually dying out and the new generation assimilates this truth literally with mother's milk".

In conclusion, I should mention the topic of physical space, as you will certainly think about it. In this short article, I cannot discuss all the theories of physical space currently accepted by the scientific world, but I will briefly outline the main criteria in understanding space. During the total solar eclipse on May 29, 1919, a group of British scientist led by Arthur Eddington carried out an experiment. The expedition discovered the deflection of light at the edge of the solar disk. The essence of the experiment may be summarized to the fact that a star, located behind the Sun, outside a straight line for an observer from Earth, became visible during an eclipse. The experiment showed the visibility of the star for an observer from the Earth that only confirms the peculiarities of light quanta behavior when passing through the sun's atmosphere. It is now generally accepted, that a ray of light or, as physicists say, a flux of photons expresses the idea of a straight line. Moreover, we all know that these photons in space behave differently. So in an ideal vacuum when a photon moves, straightness is observed, but at the same time, they are not mathematical straight lines with zero thickness, since they have wave characteristics. Light quanta have different physical properties, so passing through different inhomogeneous media other than vacuum; a ray of light can bend, refract in the form of mirages and decompose into a spectrum of waves and so on. The ray of light now and the stretched rope between two pegs in Ancient Egypt are just perceived or material things as Aristotle has characterized them.

Figure 3. Platonic solids. From left to right: tetrahedron, cube, octahedron, icosahedron and dodecahedron.

People, building the science of geometry, can only analyze the movement of a ray of light and the behavior of a stretched thread. If it is necessary to display curvilinear physical movement, we can easily reflect it in the geometry of Euclid, it's not necessary to create different geometries while violating all the rules and logic of constructing mathematics as a provable science. There is a reason why Euclid rejected ambiguity in understanding geometric things. A priori geometry allows you to have ideal points, straight lines, planes and geometrical figures, which makes it possible to build an ideal science of mathematics. All astronomers, physicists and factory workers know how difficult it is to get a telescope mirror with a surface roughness measured in nanometers. And it is generally impossible to obtain an ideal mirror surface in practice, while mathematicians denote it easily. This why the exemplary science of mathematics is needed: to reflect a real understanding of figures and space, to be a reference and a guide in the reflection of measurements, while conducting research by other sciences.

4 THE MYSTERY OF THE PARALLEL LINE THEORY

For a better understanding of geometric space, let's get acquainted with some volumetric bodies with regular polyhedra. A convex polyhedron is called regular if all its faces are regular and equal to each other, and all its dihedral angles are equal. All regular polyhedra were known in Ancient Greece. The Ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician Plato represents four ele-

ments through them: tetrahedron is fire, cube is land, icosahedron is water and octahedron is air, the fifth polyhedron dodecahedron symbolized the entire universe. Therefore, regular polyhedral are often called Platonic solids (fig. 3). Euclid pays no less attention to Platonic solids, as in his book “The elements” he devotes three books from 11th to 13th to the study of all volumetric solids. And at the very end of the essay [4, b.13, p.140] Euclid writes: “*I assert that apart from the mentioned 5 bodies it is impossible to construct another body enclosed between equilateral and equiangular polygons equal to each other*”. Based on previously proven theorems, Euclid gives a beautiful proof, confirming the uniqueness of Platonic solids and the impossibility of building other regular polyhedra. Because of the correctness of their geometric forms, the external beauty and a small number of variants of regular polyhedra, people for many centuries considered Platonic solids to be God’s creation. In the Middle Ages, believing in a single creator-God, Johannes Kepler (1571–1630) tried to substantiate the existence of the solar system and the movement of five planets through five Platonic solids. However, an attempt to reveal the secret of the universe on this hypothesis was unsuccessful. Later Kepler abandoned the intended approach in favor of a different harmony, body motions of the solar system hidden in mathematical formulas. In order to appreciate the beauty of Platonic solids in the text above there is table 1 of the characteristic and the number of elements in the figures, forming regular geometric polyhedra.

№	Regular polyhedron	Magnitude of dihedral angle, degree	Number of edges, pieces	Number of edges at apex, pieces	Number of all edges, pieces	Number of sides of a face, pieces	Number of vertices, pieces
1	Tetrahedron	70,5	4	3	6	3	4
2	Cube	90	6	3	12	4	8
3	Octahedron	109,5	8	4	12	3	6
4	Icosahedron	138,19	20	5	30	3	12
5	Dodecahedron	116,57	12	3	30	5	20

Table 1. Characteristic and the number of elements in Platonic solids.

We can see that all the many sided geometries appeared due to the adoption of the fifth Euclid’s postulate. The axiomatics of the book “The elements” is so perfect that has no significant comments and is recognized by all scientists. Which means that having completely removed the fifth postulate of parallelism from the beginnings of geometry, we can use the rest of Euclid’s axioms to construct the foundations of geometry without former flaws. Building the foundations of geometry without the fifth postulate, let’s introduce into the initial axiomatics definitions that reveal the understanding of infinity volume and geometric space. For this we will transfer some of the definitions from a solid geometry of “The elements” [4, b.11, pp.9... 10] to the axiomatics of the planimetry, stated at the beginning of the text.

Definition 24. *A body is that which has length, width and depth.*

Definition 25. *Surface is a boundary of a body.*

Definition 26. *A straight line will be perpendicular to the plane if it forms right angles with all the straight lines touching it and located on this plane (located below).*

This definition does not violate the sequence of the structure of axioms, since they are autonomous and independent of the geometry set out by Euclid in books 2 to 10. Let’s introduce

one new definition of body height and two new postulates, building on the definitions 24, 25, 26.

Definition 27. Body height is a straight line, perpendicular to the plane of the indicated length and width, it determinates the distance from the plane to the farthest point of the body boundary.

Postulate 5. Infinity in geometry is the possibility of unlimited repeatability and placement one after another of the last closed parts. Infinity is out of reach and has no border.

From the accepted definitions, we see that to determine the characteristics of a geometric body, three measurement parameters are sufficient: length, width and depth (height). Based on the foregoing and taking the logic of repetition of finite and closed parts to infinity, we designate space as having the same properties as geometric bodies.

Postulate 6. Geometric space is a three-dimensional space filled with dots that fill it evenly in length, width and height, completely without voids and limitations, that is, to infinity. There can not be emptiness due to the lack of points in some part of space.

I want to say that geometric space has existed for a long time independently of our will. Nature, through the physics of body structure and their various connections between themselves, constantly use the geometry of the space structure. Let's build a model of the geometry of space structure. Imagine we are creators and there is nothing in front of us only emptiness. We need an initial building material so that geometric lines, various surfaces and figures can exist in this void. What can be a brick of our geometry? A point for sure. Both lines and surfaces, various geometric bodies and figures consist of it; therefore the Euclidean axiomatics of geometry begins with the definition of a point.

Having been acquainted with the history of geometry construction from Euclid to the creators of non-Euclidean geometry models, we see that the model of space for everyone is built on a straight line, taken as a basis. So Euclid took as initial basis the straight line, determined by the axiomatics of the book "The elements", as the result we came across the fifth postulate, which is difficult to understand and contains a lot of mysteries. In the construction of non-Euclidean geometries, a curved straight line was taken as a basis, after that we came across many contradictions. In the text, I have already stated the statements in the absence of logic arising in the construction of a model of non-Euclidean space. In addition I will cite some of the expressed thoughts of the Soviet mathematician A. Aleksandrov, set out in chapter 9 of the book "The foundations of geometry". Criticizing David Gilbert's axioms and his view on understanding a geometric point and a straight line, he says [5, p.268]: "... *From this perspective the question of the consistency of the axioms necessarily arises*". Gilbert, in order to get away from the problems, associated with the lack of logic in the axiomatics developed by him, tries to substantiate the beginnings of geometry, using a formalized language, in which all mathematical sentences and the laws of logic are written using special symbols in the form of formulas without the participation of verbal expressions. In response to that Aleksandr Danilovich says [5, p.269]: "... *In fact such kind of formalization of the geometry foundations was not carried out, as it was later proved, it could not lead to the final proof of the consistency of geometry*". Due to the lack of provability in the structure of Gilbert's axiomatics, some mathematicians have concluded that a logically constructed geometry without contradictions cannot exist in the world. In their opinion, the axiomatics of geometry can be formed only by agreement, that is, by convention. That is why this view later received the name "conventionalism". Criticizing the views of assumptions and compromise in the construction of mathematical principles, A. Aleksandrov, at the end of

his book, writes [5, p.286]: “...Therefore, conventional geometry is put at the same rank as natural geometry no more than an invention of a different cabinet philosophy”.

To know the truth of the world’s creation, you need to answer the following questions. What does everything consist of ? What processes prompted everything to appear? At present, a large hadron collider is operating in Switzerland, where physicists disperse colliding beams of nuclear particles at a speed close to the speed of light. They study the behavior of smallest particles, obtained after a collision. It is unknown whether these smallest particles are divided into even smaller particles, since mathematics allows an infinite decrease and increase of geometric bodies. In the structure of geometry, everything is much simpler, because we know the initial small final volumetric value — a point. Lines, surfaces, geometric shapes consist of it. Having learnt the location of points in space, we will determine how and how many straight lines pass through two points on the plane and we will reveal the secret of parallel lines theory.

In the natural environment, in the wild, a person sees only the outer form of bodies and smells some gases. Only with the invention of microscopes, we have been able to see the movement of molecules and the arrangement of atoms in material things. We are considering the structure of the geometry principles, a point according to the definition of Euclid’s axiomatics

Figure 4. Arrangement of five tetrahedrons in space around one edge.

is something that has no parts, and then in order to see geometric points, we must mentally imagine them by looking with a microscope that magnifies an infinite number of times. Mentally enlarging a small part of space an infinite number of times, we will be able to unravel the mystery of the already existing geometry of space. In the postulate 6, we have said that space consists of evenly spaced points without voids that is why we immediately pay attention to regular polyhedra. The vertexes will represent points and the edges will indicate the size of the increasing an infinite number of times. There are no edges in our model; they determine the uniformity of the location of points in space. Let’s analyze all five Platonic solids (fig. 3). Icosahedron and dodecahedron are some of the largest in body volume. Of course, it is inefficient to fill the space with such arrangement of points, because additional points can be placed inside these figures. Octahedron is uneven in the location of the points, as in the center of its contour the vertexes are located in the shape of a square, the vertexes above and below are located in the shape of an equilateral triangle. Only tetrahedron and cube are left in terms of efficient filling. Reasoning from the position of efficient filling of space, one would like to give preference to tetrahedron, as it fills the initial geometric space most efficiently. Let’s carry out the following construction, and we know one regular tetrahedron $AEDB$ (fig. 4). The point F is the midpoint

of the edge DE , and then the segments BF and AF are perpendiculars to the edge DE . Which means that the angle BFA is dihedral and equal to $70,5^\circ$ (table 1). By analogy with tetrahedron $AEDB$, let's create four more equal to it. Making five tetrahedrons around one common edge DE , as shown in figure 4, we will find that the space is not completely filled. We have an unfilled sector with a dihedral angle BFC equal to $7,5^\circ$, which is unacceptable to the requirement of the sixth postulate about space. Let's do the same filling around one edge with the rest of the shapes. Summing up the value of the dihedral angle, when composing the Platonic solids, we come to the only possible option — filling the space with points in the form of a cube. As the sum of four dihedral angles of a cube is 360° . The space is filled with cube-shaped points evenly and without voids, which meets the requirements of postulate 6. In order to understand space, let's build a model of points location in the space. For this, we will depict eight composed cubes as shown in the figure 5. In which the vertices of the cube are points in the space, and the edges indicate the amount of infinite increase. The picture shows, that the

Figure 5. Geometric space model, filled with cube-shaped points.

points, filling the space in the form of a cube, form two options for constructing a plane. The first version of the plane is close in understanding to the Euclidean plane and represents a checkered sheet of paper. In the second variant, the plane does not have a flat appearance and the points on it are arranged in volume; it is easier to say that a flat surface has irregularities of no more than one point in size. We will reveal the secret and find out how many lines pass through two distant points in this volumetric plan. For this, consider two squares, forming a volumetric plane, which are composed of the squares $ADHBWCGK$ and $KMOPVTSL$. Imagine how the points of a straight line, passing through the points A, K and L in figure 5 can be located. As we can see, three edges a, b and c come from point A , it means that three directions of the location of points come from each “volumetric” plane, creating a straight line AKL :

1. A straight line AKL is made up of points — $ADHKMOL$;
2. A straight line AKL is made up of points — $ACGKTSL$;
3. A straight line AKL is made up of points — $ABWKPVL$.

From the indicated order of points arrangement, it follows that three straight lines pass through two distant points of the “volumetric” plane of space.

Consider the first option with a flat plane. In figure 6, we see that on a flat version of the plane there are mutually perpendicular and parallel straight lines, they are the straight lines ATD, GNK, AGM and TNP , which fully reflect the structure of straight lines in the unchanged axiomatics of Euclidean geometry. They are perfectly straight and the points on the line are located sequentially one after the other, and only one straight line passes through two points of these straight lines. Consider the plane sector DAH (fig. 6) separately. An imaginary straight

line AB divides the sector into two equal parts. The straight line is formed by two variants of the symmetrical arrangement of points, which means that two straight lines pass through two separate points on the considered section of the plane. Consider a straight line AC of the same plane, which is located in a sector with an angle of inclination not equal to 45° , and the points on it are in the sequence shown in picture 6. One straight line is most likely passes through points A and C , although this is not so important for us. The main thing is that we know the model of the location of points in the space, the rules for the location of points when transforming straight lines can be discussed separately if necessary.

During further study of the geometry of space, we certainly cannot depict an infinite straight line with consecutive points along the entire length between two points distant from each other. The conditions of infinity of a straight line are reflected in definition 2 and postulates 2 and 6 of the axiomatics we have adopted. These requirements are necessary for the mandatory observance of the property of a straight line along its entire length. Therefore, based on the conditions laid down in the definitions and postulates of a point, a straight line and space, we may say with confidence that the structure of point's location in a small area of space, increased in an infinite number of times, will reflect the nature of the behavior of primary geometry objects throughout the space to infinity.

Figure 6. The version of a flat plane of geometric space.

For deeper understanding of space, we will solve one problem in the style of understanding the text by Euclid, the solution of which will fill the void in the absence of the parallel lines postulate in the foundations of geometry.

Proposal 1a. I claim that two straight lines, lying on the same plane, will be parallel if the reconstructed perpendicular at any point of one of the straight lines contains a segment of constant length along the entire length between straight lines to infinity. If the condition above is not fulfilled, any otherwise formed straight lines intersect with each other.

To solve this problem, consider a simpler plane from the geometric space models, this is the arrangement of points in a flat plane (fig. 7). It can be seen in the picture that a straight line segment AM consists of 7 points, located perpendicularly between straight lines MN and AH . The structure of the point locations on a given plane forms a perpendicular segment between two straight lines MN and AH , permanent and equal to 7 points throughout to infinity. Which means that straight lines will never intersect, they are parallel to each other. Achieving this target, we know that straight lines extend infinitely in space. The segment AM always has a finite measurement value between straight lines MN and AH . As soon as we define a point on the plane

for the passing of parallel straight lines, the segment AM acquires the properties of its finiteness when determining the length. Figure 7 shows the segment AM with the length of 7 points, but it can change the magnitude of a hundred or a thousand points, it doesn't matter. Retreating to the point Y of a straight line MN one point down, the segment AM at this point will decrease at one point; let's draw through it and point M an imaginary straight line. Let's trace how the points are located, forming this imaginary straight line in the geometric plane. An oblique straight line is formed in the following sequence: it is made up of points M and D' , then there is a transition down to the point D , then there is a horizontal row of points to point C' . Then a straight line segment is created by points, passing through the point $CE'EF'FG'GH'HL$, where at point L it intersects the straight line AN . It is clear from the model, that it does not matter at what distance from the considered point M of the straight line MN we decrease the distance by one point, the result will always be the same. Any inclined line, intersecting the line MN at the point M , will also intersect the second parallel line at the point L . This result comes from the definition of a straight line and a segment laid down in the axiomatics, which means the segment AM is the part of the straight line, it has a finite length and straight lines are infinite. It turns out that any inclined straight line, passing through the point M , always intersects the second parallel line AH . From the adopted definitions and the model built on their basis, one can see the completeness of the statements of the problem. For a broader perception of the solution to a problem, let's mentally study other possible options for which new parallel lines may appear.

Figure 7. Parallel straight lines in the flat plane of geometric space.

Imagine that figure 7 shows the practical geometry of space, which we use constantly in our lives, in which the points of any straight line are located sequentially, but we do not see them. Then all linear dimensions of this scheme of parallel lines will be measured in meters or kilometers, it doesn't matter. Anyway, due to the fact that the segment AM will be a finite value, and straight parallel lines AH and MN are infinite, according to their definition, we will come to a result similar to the real geometric space, which was stated above. The inclined straight line, intersecting the straight line MN at the point M , also intersects the second parallel AH at the point L , because only the unit of measurement changes. Instead of the points discussed earlier in figure 7, we are considering linear dimensions in metric units.

Let's consider another possible option — the passing of parallel lines on the plane of practical space geometry. We will depict in figure 7 new conditions for the placement of straight lines and segments. Let me remind you that the segment is a part of a straight line and therefore it is not infinite. For our imaginary experiment, the segment AM will be measured in meters. At a metric distance from point M , a straight line DMN , we will show one point Z of the real plane, which is below line DMN by one point. Based on the accepted construction conditions, the segment AM has a metric length, which means it will consist of an infinite number of points. Endlessly

changing the location of points Z along the straight line DM , we will have an infinite number of straight lines that do not intersect the straight line AH , but intersect the straight line DMN at the point M , which means they are parallel to the straight line TAH . Well, this assumption is incorrect, because we have combined two different units of measurement in one considered system of space. A point and a meter are different units of measurement and they can be considered only in an integral and separate system of measuring space.

5 CONCLUSIONS

From the model of the geometric space and the proposal 1a, it can be seen that Nikolai Lobachevsky's decision to change the edition of the fifth postulate to the opposite Euclidean statement is false, and the variety of models and new interpretations of the geometry foundations, proposed later, is nothing more than a fantasy of individual mathematicians. The created model of space replaces the need for Euclid's fifth postulate and is built based on the conditions we have adopted, specified in the axioms, definitions, postulates — of a point, space, a straight line and a segment. This suggests that through any two separate points of the geometric space, depending on their location in space, one, two or three straight lines can pass. The same condition is also true for parallel lines. No more than three parallel straight lines pass through some point lying outside the straight line under consideration on the same plane.

I would like to add, that in nature pure iron has the ideal geometry of filling space. Iron has the crystal lattice, whose atoms fill the space in the form of a cube. I would also like to underline that iron is a border metal. In nuclear fusion, starting from the conversion of hydrogen into helium and up to the formation of manganese, chemical elements are formed with the release of heat. Starting from the iron atom during the formation of heavier elements, energy is not released but consumed. These facts of nature, only confirm the correctness of our research and show the unity of geometry with the material world. Currently, astronomers can look into the distance of 45,6 billion light years using space telescopes. Using microwave radiation analysis, knowing the size of the spots and distance to them and measuring their apparent angular size from the Earth, astrophysicists get a giant triangle. The results of these measurements show that our Universe is flat with incredible accuracy — the error is less than 1%. This once again confirms that physical space is flat and obeys Euclidean geometry.

This article had solved the problem of knowing the truth of the theory of parallel lines. The old and accepted by the scientific world axiomatics of Euclidean geometry, except for the fifth postulate, is used here. Instead of the fifth postulate, two new postulates of understanding infinity and geometric space have been introduced. A new model of the geometry of space is being built. While studying the model, the mystery of the fifth postulate, the secrets of building straight lines and geometric figures are revealed. We have determined that through any two distant points in space one, two or three straight lines can pass at the same time. Their number depends only on the adoption of a fixed position in the space of the geometric model. Based on the research presented in the article, we come to the recognition that the definitions in Euclid's axiomatics have the same status as postulates and axioms. We cannot remove them, deviation from these rules will lead the axiomatics to absurdity in all science. All proposed models are part of space and are included in the geometric model of space from points, which is unique, has no contradictions and is confirmed by Euclid's axiomatics.

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